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FORMULATION OPTIMIZATION AND *IN-VITRO* EVALUATION OF NANOSTRUCTURED LIPID CARRIER CONTAINING ANTIPSYCHOTIC DRUG

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of the present work is to formulate, optimize and evaluate a Nanostructured Lipid Carrier (NLC) of a poorly water soluble antipsychotic drug: Ziprasidone hydrochloride monohydrate (ZHM) by high shear homogenization technique followed by ultrasonication method to enhance the oral bioavailability. ZHM a dopamine receptor antagonist, is an orally active atypical antipsychotic drug used in the treatment of schizophrenia and bipolar disorder. ZHM is a BCS Class II drug which is poorly water-soluble so its oral bioavailability is 60% when administered with food. The absorption of ZHM is increased up to two-fold in the presence of food. Preformulation studies including screening of excipients for solubility suggested the suitability of precirol ATO 5 as solid lipid, labrafil M1944 as liquid lipid and gelucire 50/13 as stabilizer for preparation of NLC. The optimized ZHM-NLC was characterised by measuring particle size, drug entrapment efficiency and *in vitro* drug release. The concentration of solid lipid and liquid lipid in the ratio of 70:30 was optimised as final formulation components concentration as it exhibited desired mean particle size (200-302 nm) and % Entrapment efficiency (54-84%). The *in vitro* drug release study indicated the ZHM-NLC sustained release formulation showed sustained release profile of 98.62 % release within 24 hours. Based on this results it was concluded that NLCs are promising drug delivery for improving the oral bioavailability of ZHM.

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INTRODUCTION

Schizophrenia is a serious disorder which affects how a person thinks, feels and acts. Someone with schizophrenia may have difficulty distinguishing between what is real and what is imaginary; may be unresponsive or withdrawn; and may have difficulty expressing normal emotions in social situations. The cause of schizophrenia is still unclear. Some theories about the cause of this disease include: genetics (heredity), biology (the imbalance in the brain's chemistry); and/or possible viral infections and immune disorders. Schizophrenia affects about 1% of the world population. In the United States one in a hundred people, about 2.5 million have this disease. It knows no racial, cultural or economic boundaries. Symptoms usually appear between the ages of 13 and 25, but often appear earlier in males than females^[1]. Lipid nanoparticles based on solid matrix have emerged as potential drug carriers to improve gastrointestinal (GI) absorption and oral bioavailability of several drugs, especially lipophilic compounds. These formulations may also be used for sustained drug release. Lipid-based drug delivery systems may contain a broad range of oils, surfactants, and co-solvents. They represent one of the most popular approaches to overcome the absorption barriers and to improve the bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs. Lipid formulations can reduce the inherent limitation of slow and incomplete dissolution of poorly water-soluble drugs and facilitate formation of solubilized phases from which absorption may occur. The co-administration of lipids with drugs can also impact their absorption pathway although most orally administered compounds gain access to the systemic circulation via the portal vein, some highly lipophilic drugs are transported directly to the systemic circulation via intestinal lymphatics, which improves oral bioavailability of API^[2]. According to National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guidelines (2002) oral atypical antipsychotics are recommended as first-line treatment for patients with newly diagnosed schizophrenia^[3, 4]. ZHM (figure 1) is a new atypical antipsychotic, proved to be effective in the treatment of schizophrenia and do not cause agranulocytosis. It has a low potential for extrapyramidal side effects as compared to other antipsychotic drugs. Ziprasidone hydrochloride monohydrate (ZHM), a dopamine receptor antagonist, is an orally active atypical antipsychotic drug used in the treatment of schizophrenia and bipolar disorder. ZHM belongs to a group of benz-isothiazoylpiperazine derivative^[5, 6] that was developed from the chemically related antipsychotic tiospirone^[3]. ZHM is chemically known as 5-[2-[4-(1, 2-benzothiazol-3-yl) piperazin-1-yl] ethyl]-6-chloro-1,3-dihydroindol-2-one hydrochloride.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Ziprasidone hydrochloride Monohydrate (ZHM).

Ziprasidone is the fifth atypical antipsychotic approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration for the treatment of schizophrenia, and acute mania and mixed states associated with bipolar disorder.

ZHM is supplied in capsule dosage form for oral administration in following strengths of 20 mg, 60mg, and 80mg.

ZHM is a BCS Class II drug which is poorly water-soluble; its solubility in water is 0.3 mg/ml. The solubility decreases with increasing pH owing to its pKa (approx. 6) value^[7].

The oral bioavailability of ZHM is 60% when administered with food. The absorption of ZHM is increased up to two-fold in the presence of food^[8]. ZHM is reported to have short biological half-life (7hrs.) necessitating its administration two to three times a day. Thus it is a potential candidate for the development of sustained release (SR) formulations.

SR formulations of ZHM will release drug slowly for maximum period of time and maintain plasma level of drug for 12-24 hrs. as a result it may improve the therapeutic effect, and it can also reduce food effect and dosing frequency.

In order to achieve sustained or controlled release of ZHM with enhanced bioavailability and no food effect, conventional matrix or coating-based delivery systems may be proposed, which however are bound to be useless because the drug is poorly water-soluble, thus an attempt is made to develop novel Nanostructured Lipid Carrier (NLC) system loaded with ZHM to enhance its oral bioavailability. The objectives were set to design and develop a novel NLC based oral SR formulation of ZHM.

Objective:

Primary objective of the research work was to develop and evaluate NLCs based oral formulation containing ZHM in a novel drug delivery system (SLN/NLC system).

To achieve primary objective work was planned as follows:-

- To screen various lipids, oils and surfactants to select most suitable excipients for the formulation of SLN/ NLC dispersion of ZHM.
- To develop and validate analytical methods [reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method and high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC) method] for the quantitative analysis during formulation development studies of ZHM loaded SLN/ NLC dispersion and capsules.
- To formulate Ziprasidone Hydrochloride Monohydrate (ZHM) loaded SLN/ NLC based dispersion and final dosage form (capsules).
- To characterize ZHM loaded NLCs formulations in terms of particle size, polydispersity index, entrapment efficiency, *In vitro* drug release.
- To study crystallographic investigation through X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and Differential Scanning Colorimetry (DSC).
- To compare the dissolution profile of ZHM loaded NLC based capsule and marketed sustained released formulation.
- To carry out the short term stability study of the final formulation as per the recommendation of ICH guidelines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Materials**

Ziprasidone hydrochloride Monohydrate [ZHM] was obtained as generous gift sample from Wockhardt Limited, Mumbai. Solid lipids such as Precirol ATO 5 (Glyceryl palmitostearate), Compritol 888 ATO; Gelot and Geleol was obtained from Gattefosse, France; Stearic acid, Imwitor 900 K, Glyceryl monostearate and Dynasan 114 was obtained from CREMER OLEO GmbH & Co, Germany. Liquid lipids such as Capmul MCM was obtained from Abitec corporation, USA; Labrafil M2125 and Labrafil M1944 (Apricot kernel oil PEG-6 ester), Capryol 90 was obtained from Gattefosse, France; Labrafac, Oleic acid, Ethyl oleate was obtained from S.D. Fine, Mumbai, India; Castor oil was obtained from. Stabilizers such as Gelucire 50/13 (Stearoyl macrogol 32 glycerides) and Gelucire 44/14 was obtained from Gattefosse, France. Unless otherwise stated all other materials were of analytical grade.

Method**Screening of solid lipid**

Solubility of the drug in a lipid is a key factor to achieve high entrapment of the drug into the lipid matrix. Therefore, solubility of ZHM in various lipids was determined in order to determine the lipid having maximum potential to solubilize the drug. For studying the solubility in solid lipids, accurately weighed 10 mg of ZHM was taken in a series of test tubes, the solid lipids were added in increments, and the test tubes were heated in a controlled temperature water bath kept at 10°C above the melting point of the respective lipid. The test tubes were intermittently vortexed using cyclone mixer and observed for any drug residue. The amount of lipid required to completely solubilize the drug in the molten state was estimated. Solid lipids such as Compritol 888 ATO, Stearic acid, Gelot, Geleol, Precirol ATO 5, Imwitor 900 K, Glyceryl monostearate and Dynasan 114 were screened for preparation of ZHM-NLC dispersion^[9].

Screening of liquid lipids

Liquid lipid or oil for the preparation of NLC was selected based on the relative drug solubility. The method adopted for the determination of solubility of drug in oil was similar to the methods used in microemulsions or self-emulsifying systems. The fixed volume (2 ml) of different oils was taken in glass vials separately. An excess amount of drug was added to each vial till saturation of oil and mixed using cyclone mixer. After tightly capping, these vials were kept on mechanical shaker for the period of 72 hours at room temperature. If the entire drug in vial was dissolved in respective oil then more amount of drug was added during the period of 48 hours. After that, it was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for the period of 30 minutes to separate the undissolved drug. The supernatant thus obtained was then filtered through membrane filter (0.45 µ). The filtrate was diluted appropriately with methanol and absorbance was recorded by UV spectroscopy at the wavelength of 317 nm. The solubility of ZHM (mg/ml) in oils was determined by back calculation. Liquid lipids such as Capmul MCM, Labrafac, Oleic acid, Ethyl oleate, Castor oil, Capryol 90, Labrafil M1944 and Labrafil M2125 were screened for formulation of NLC dispersion^[10].

Selection of stabilizer

The choice of the surfactants/stabilizers and their concentration has a great impact on the quality of the lipid nanoparticles dispersion. High concentrations of the emulsifier reduce the surface tension and facilitate the particle partition during formation. The decrease in particle size is connected with a tremendous increase in surface area. So it is very important to select proper surfactant with the respective drug. Briefly, Precirol ATO 5 in varying concentration of 350, 420, 490mg, Gelucire 50/13 and Gelucire 44/14 in concentration of 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 400, 450, 500 mg, and the selected oil (Labrafil M1944) in concentration of 350, 280, 210 mg were transferred to different test tubes. These test tubes were heated to 90°C and the temperature was maintained at 90°C. Double distilled water, 9.3 ml, was transferred to another test tube and the test tube was heated to the same temperature as that of lipid phase. The aqueous phase was added at once to the lipid phase under cyclomixing (~1200 rpm) which was continued until a uniform crude emulsion was formed. The crude emulsion was sonicated using a probe sonicator at 30 W for 15 min (Oscar ultrasonics, Mumbai, India). The resulting nanoemulsion was cooled to room temperature by intermittent shaking. The resultant dispersions were evaluated visually for evidence of phase separation. The particle size of the lipid dispersions was measured using photon correlation spectroscopy. All the experiments were carried out in triplicate. The particle size and polydispersity index of the NLC were evaluated by PCS. The NLC dispersion was further evaluated for the stability of formulation, % EE and particles size to finalise its use as stabilizer and also to optimise concentration for the preparation of NLCs dispersion. The pre-emulsions were prepared using varying concentrations of Gelucire 50/13 and Gelucire 44/14 from 100-400 mg, while keeping concentration of drug and Lmix constant ^[11] as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition of Pre-emulsion stabilizer concentration.

Stabilizer	Batch No.	Drug (mg)	Lmix (mg)	Stabilizer quantity (mg)	Distilled Water q.s to (mg)
Gelucire 50/13	G1	40	600	100	10
	G2	40	600	150	10
	G3	40	600	200	10
	G4	40	600	250	10
	G5	40	600	300	10
	G6	40	600	350	10
	G7	40	600	400	10
Gelucire 40/14	H1	40	600	100	10
	H2	40	600	150	10
	H3	40	600	200	10
	H4	40	600	250	10
	H5	40	600	300	10
	H6	40	600	350	10
	H7	40	600	400	10

Selection of solid lipid to liquid lipid ratio (Lmix ratio)

The solid and liquid lipid with the best-solubilizing potential for ZHM i.e., Precirol ATO 5 and Labrafil M1944 were mixed in different ratios viz., 4.4:0.5, 4:1, 3.5:1.5, 3:2 in order to establish the miscibility of the two lipids. The total amount of lipid selected for use was 600 mg. The lipid mixtures were kept at 85°C for 1 hour in water bath shaker. After that the samples were allowed to cool at room temperature. The miscibility between the two components was investigated by smearing a cooled sample of the solid mixture onto hydrophilic filter paper, followed by visual observation to determine the presence of any liquid oil droplets on the filter paper. A binary mixture exhibiting a melting point above 40°C and which did not reveal the presence of oil droplets on the filter paper was selected for use in the development of ZHM-loaded NLCs ^[12]. Three batches having different solid lipid to liquid lipid ratio 4:1, 3.5:1.5, 3:2 (w/w) were designed as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Selection of solid lipid: liquid lipid ratio.

Batch Code	Drug (mg)	Solid lipid: Liquid lipid (Lmix) (600 mg)	Pricerol ATO 5 (mg)	Oil (mg)	Gelucire 50/13 (mg)	Distilled Water q.s to (ml)
NS1	40	4:1	480	120	250	10
NS2	40	3.5:1.5	420	180	250	10
NS3	40	3:2	360	240	250	10

Method of preparation of NLCs dispersion

High shear homogenization with ultrasonication technique was used to prepare NLCs dispersion. An accurately weighed solid lipid (Precirol ATO 5), liquid lipid (oleic acid) and stabilizer (Gelucire 50/13) were first mixed together in a glass vial along with the drug and then heated at 70-80°C (5-10°C above the melting point of lipid mixture) on a water bath. The melted lipid mixture and drug were mixed properly to fully dissolve the drug in melted lipid mixture so as to obtain a clear melting solution. In separate beaker double distilled water was heated at 70-80°C. Then this hot aqueous phase maintained at same temperature was poured in the melted lipid mixture containing drug (oil phase). The mixture was high shear homogenised using a homogenizer (IKA T-10 Ultra Turrax, Germany) at 9,000 rpm for 15 minutes, while maintaining the temperature at 70-80°C. The coarse o/w emulsion is formed which was further sonicated for 15 minutes at ultrasonication power of 20 Watt using Sonapros PR-250 M (Oscar Ultrasonics, Mumbai). The resulting o/w nanoemulsions was immediately placed in ice bath maintained at 2-4°C to cool it down rapidly under magnetic stirring for 10-15 minutes. The liquid nanodroplets of melted lipid transformed into solid nanoparticles at low temperature and leads to formation of NLCs dispersion. After cooling, it was stored in refrigerator in cool condition as the shelf life of NLCs dispersion is more at cool condition as compared to room temperature^[13, 14]. The schematic representation of preparation of NLC dispersion is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of preparation of NLC dispersion by HSH coupled with US.

Optimization of NLC Dispersion^[15]

A 3² randomized full factorial design was employed for carrying out the optimization of NLCs. Based on the results obtained in preliminary studies, amount of total lipid [X1] (i.e. Solid lipid and liquid lipid) and concentration of stabilizer [X2] were found to be the major variables in determining the entrapment efficiency (% EE) and mean particle size (MPS). So, these variables were selected as independent variables to obtain an optimised formula for maximum % EE and minimum MPS using 3² factorial design. The effect of these independent variables was investigated on two dependent variables, namely % EE [Y1] and MPS [Y2] to evaluate the responses. The optimization was done by using the Design-Expert® software (Version 9.0.4.0; Stat-Ease; Inc.; MN; USA). The operating conditions i.e. the rpm and time of Ultra Turrax as well as the time and power for ultrasonication during preparation of NLC dispersion were adjusted based on the results obtained in preliminary study and were later kept constant during the runs of optimization batches. The pre-emulsification by Ultra Turrax was performed at 9,000 rpm for 15 minutes, followed by ultrasonication at 20 Watt using Sonapros PR-250 M (Oscar Ultrasonics, Mumbai) for 15 minutes.

Coded values and actual values of two independent variables, amount of total lipid [X1] and stabilizer concentration [X2] are represented in Table 3. The experimental trials were performed in all 9 possible combinations as shown in Table 4. These nine formulations were evaluated for % EE and mean particle size. On the basis of their results, overlay plots, contour plots and surface response plots were obtained.

Table 3: Coded and actual values of factorial design.

Factor	Level		
	Low (-1)	Medium (0)	High (+1)
Independent variables			
Total lipid concentration (mg) [X1]	500	600	700
Stabilizer (Gelucire 50/13) concentration (mg) [X2]	200	250	300

Table 4: Formulation of NLCs dispersion using 3² factorial design.

No. of Run	Coded Levels	Quantity of drug (mg)	Quantity of Total lipid (mg) [X1]	Quantity of Surfactant (mg) [X2]	DW q.s. to (ml)
1	-1,-1	40	500	200	10
2	-1,0	40	500	250	10
3	-1,+1	40	500	300	10
4	0,-1	40	600	200	10
5	0,0	40	600	250	10
6	0,+1	40	600	300	10
7	+1,-1	40	700	200	10
8	+1,0	40	700	250	10
9	+1,+1	40	700	300	10

Suitable mathematical models of the mixture design such as linear, quadratic, and special cubic models were analysed by the software. Significance of the model was determined by comparisons of statistical parameters like standard deviation (SD), the multiple correlation coefficient (R²), adjusted multiple correlation coefficient (adjusted R²), predicted multiple correlation coefficient (predicted R²) and predicted residual error sum of squares (PRESS). The best model was decided on the basis of higher values of adjusted R² and predicted R².

The predicted R² should fall no more than 0.2 below the adjusted R². PRESS value should be small for the best model. PRESS value demonstrates how well the model fits the data.

Selection of cryoprotectant

Cryoprotectants have been added, in order to prevent aggregation of nanoparticles and ensure re-dispersibility after freeze-thawing. Commonly used cryoprotectants are sucrose, trehalose and mannitol. The cryoprotectant was selected on the basis of appearance of freeze dried product, particle size obtained after redispersion and entrapment efficiency. Cryoprotectant is selected in such a way that final lyophilized powder should have a cake-shaped appearance without shrinkage and there should not be increase in particle size to larger extent.

Optimized batches of 10 ml of NLCs dispersion were freeze dried with various cryoprotectants such as D-mannitol, trehalose and sucrose in various concentrations such as 1 %, 1.5 % and 3 %.

To prepare lyophilized ZHM-NLCs powder, these cryoprotectants in different concentrations were added to NLCs dispersion and solutions were filled into glass vials. All glass vials were pre-frozen in deep freezer at -20°C for 24 h then the freeze drying was carried out using freeze dryer (Christ, Alpha 1-2 LD plus, Germany) at -55°C and pressure of 0.001 mbar for 24 h. The obtained freeze dried product was evaluated for appearance, %EE and particle size on reconstitution of the dry powder.

Evaluation and characterization of NLC

a) % Entrapment efficiency (% EE)

Entrapment efficiency corresponds to the percentage of drug encapsulated within and adsorbed onto the nanoparticles. The entrapment efficiency (% EE) was determined by measuring the concentration of untrapped drug in the lipidic dispersions. The dispersion formed was destabilised by diluting appropriately with saturated sodium chloride solution.

Appropriately diluted lipid dispersion was subjected to centrifugation for 30 minutes at 10,000 rpm. After centrifugation (Remi instruments, India) of resultant dispersion, the amount of free drug in the supernatant was estimated by using UV/VIS spectrophotometer at wavelength of 317 nm. The amount of incorporated drug was determined as the difference between the initial drug content and free drug in the supernatant. Experiment was done in triplicate.

$$EE (\%) = \frac{W_{\text{initial drug}} - W_{\text{free drug}}}{W_{\text{initial drug}}} \times 100$$

b) Particle size analysis

Particle size (z-average diameter) and poly dispersity index (PDI) of the NLCs were measured by dynamic light scattering technique using NAOPHOX particle size analyzer (Sympatec, GmbH, Germany). Before measurement, the nanoparticle dispersion was diluted appropriately to yield a suitable intensity (particle count rate between 100 and 1000 kbps) with ultra-pure water. These diluted NLCs dispersion was poured into the cuvette which was then placed in the cuvette holder of the instruments and analysed using Nanoprox software. All measurements were done in triplicate.

c) In-vitro drug release study

Drug release of ZHM from optimized NLCs dispersion was studied using dialysis membrane bag in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer (900 ml)^[16, 17] with 0.5% SLS using USP XXIII dissolution testing apparatus type II (LABINDIA DS 8000 autosampler dissolution test apparatus) with rotating paddle at 50 rpm and bath temperature was maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. 5 ml of optimized NLCs dispersion equivalent to 40mg of ZHM was used in dissolution study. The NLCs dispersion was filled in dialysis membrane -70 which was soaked previously in double distilled water for 24 h and it was tied to the paddle of dissolution apparatus. 5ml samples were withdrawn at different time intervals of 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16 and 24 h from dissolution medium and replaced with 5 ml of fresh buffer maintained at same temperature in order to maintain sink condition. The aliquots withdrawn were filtered through syringe filters. The filtrate was injected into the column and assayed for ZHM content using validated HPLC method. By determining the amount of ZHM released at various time intervals. After determining the contents, the % release versus time graphs was plotted for optimized NLCs dispersion.

d) X-ray diffraction study

X-ray scattering measurements were carried out with Pan-analytical Xpert PRO MPD X-ray diffractometer. Anode material used was copper having $K\alpha_1$ and $K\alpha_2$ radiation wavelength of 1.5405 and 1.5444 respectively with generator voltage of 45 KV and tube current of 40 mA and detected using Xcelerator diffracted beam monochromator. X-ray diffraction was carried out on pure ZHM, Lmix (Precirol ATO 5 and Labrafil M1944), blank freeze dried NLC and drug loaded freeze dried NLC.

e) DSC study

DSC study was carried out mainly to evaluate the compalibility of drug with all the excipients as well as to confirm the entrapment of drug in NLC. Thermogram of the lyophilized powder sample of NLCs was studied. An empty aluminium pan was used as a reference. DSC measurements were performed at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{minute}$ from 25 to 350°C using aluminum sealed pan. The sample size was 5-10 mg for each measurement. During the measurement, the sample cell was purged with nitrogen gas.

f) Stability studies

The purpose of stability studies is to ascertain how the quality of a medicinal product varies as a function of time and under the influence of variety of environmental factors.

Protocol for Stability Testing

Time span of study: 3 months

Temperature and humidity condition:

The stability studies will be conducted as per the condition recommended in ICH guidelines for a period of 3 months at the following storage conditions.

1. $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 65 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$
2. $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 75 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$

Sampling points:

The samples were taken after 0 days, 30 days, 60 days and 90 days.

Parameters evaluated:

The stability batches were evaluated for appearance, *in-vitro* drug release study, entrapment efficiency and particle size.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Screening of solid lipids**

Solid lipid was selected on the basis of stability of dispersion, ability to solubilize maximum amount of drug and physical compatibility with liquid lipid and drug. Among the various solid lipids screened, Precirol ATO 5 showed highest solubility for ZHM, as shown in figure 3. 314.80 mg of Precirol ATO 5 was optimized for the formulation of NLC dispersion. Hence, it was selected as preferred lipid for formulation and development studies. For the pre-optimization study, the amount of Precirol ATO 5 was taken on the basis of drug solubility in lipid.

Figure 3: Amount of solid lipid required to solubilize 10 mg of ZHM.

Screening of liquid lipid

Among the various liquid lipids screened, Labrafil M1944 showed highest solubility for ZHM as shown in figure 4. Hence Labrafil M1944 was considered as the best choice for the preparation of NLCs to maximize the entrapment of drug.

Figure 4: Solubility of ZHM in different oils.

Selection of stabilizer ^[11]

Solubility of ZHM in various stabilizers with varying concentrations is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Pre-optimization for selection of stabilizer concentration.

Stabilizer	Concentration (mg)	Particle Size (nm)	Entrapment Efficiency (%)	Observations after 12 hours
Gelucire 50/13	100	335.20	85.23	Aggregation of particles
	150	315.80	84.46	Aggregation of particles
	200	216.80	83.05	Stable
	250	245.26	82.66	Stable
	300	234.43	80.08	Stable
	350	200.48	76.89	Phase separation
	400	190.96	71.34	Phase separation
Gelucire 44/14	100	233.37	72.52	Phase separation
	150	221.07	70.33	Phase separation
	200	220.99	69.21	Phase separation
	250	212.22	67.80	Phase separation
	300	200.48	65.90	Phase separation
	350	190.96	62.18	Phase separation
	400	165.59	60.08	Phase separation

Generally stabilizer composition exhibiting good entrapment efficiency and least mean particle size materialize the drug moieties in the lipid core and impart firm association of drug with the lipid matrix. So, generally stabilizer concentration exhibiting optimum particle size with desired entrapment efficiency for ZHM-NLC dispersion is preferred. Hence, these stabilizer concentrations were selected and assessed further for their stabilizing property.

From the above table it was concluded that Gelucire 50/13 is more compatible with the drug and was also found to be stable after 24 hrs as compared to Gelucire 44/14 as phase separation was observed for Gelucire 44/14 at the end of 24 hrs. Also, ZHM-NLC dispersion exhibited optimum mean particle size and high entrapment efficiency with Gelucire 50/13. Among various concentrations of Gelucire 50/13, 200, 250 and 300 mg were confirmed for further optimization.

Formulation and development of NLC Dispersion

Selection of solid lipid to liquid lipid ratio

All the binary mixtures of Precirol ATO 5 and Labrafil M1944 studied exhibited melting points above 40°C. In terms of visual assessment, for the binary mixtures of ratios 90:10 to 60:40, no oil droplets were seen on samples smeared on filter paper. Only in the binary mixture of ratio 50: 50, droplets of oil were observed on the filter paper. These observations suggest that a lower degree of miscibility exists between Precirol ATO 5 and Labrafil M1944 when more than 30% w/w of the liquid lipid is mixed with the solid lipid.

It may be desirable to have relatively high liquid lipid content in a binary mixture of Precirol ATO 5 and Labrafil M1944 in order to enhance the solubility of ZHM in the lipid medium as the drug exhibits a marginally better solubility profile in the liquid lipid than in solid lipids. However, the results suggest that a liquid lipid content of 30% w/w or less was optimal and concentrations higher than 30% w/w are likely to result in the production of immiscible mixtures.

The % entrapment efficiency (EE) of different batches of NLCs having the ratio of solid lipid: liquid lipid from 80: 20 to 60: 40 (i.e. 4:1 to 3:2) is shown in the table 6. It is clear from the data obtained that as the ratio of solid lipid to liquid lipid was increased from 80: 20 to 70: 30, the % EE was increased from 74.3 to 79.62. However, when the formulation contains more than 30% w/w of Labrafil M1944, the % EE was decreased to 71.39. This is because at higher contents of the liquid lipid, a part of the liquid lipid was expelled from the crystal lattice of the solid fat, which can lead to partitioning of drug in the aqueous phase, thereby decreasing the entrapment efficiency.

Table 6: % EE of different solid lipid: liquid lipid ratio.

Batch No.	Precirol ATO 5: Capryol 90	% Entrapment efficiency	Mean Particle Size
NS1	80:20 (4:1)	74.30	241.62
NS2	70:30 (3.5:2.5)	79.62	223.81
NS3	60:40 (3:2)	71.39	212.60

Key: (NS- Nanostructure batches).

From the above observations it was concluded that solid lipid and liquid lipid in the ratio of 70:30 (3.5:2.5) was optimised as final formulation components concentration as it exhibited desired mean particle size and % Entrapment efficiency.

Method of preparation of NLCs dispersion

NLC dispersion was successfully prepared according to the method described in experimental.

Optimization and characterization of NLCs Dispersion

Optimization

Optimization of NLCs Dispersion was carried out using 3² Factorial Design.

Optimization of NLC Dispersion

3² Factorial Design showed the following responses for nine batches of NLC dispersion given in table 7.

Table7: Responses for various batches of NLCs dispersion.

Batch Code.	Coded levels	Quantity of Total Lipid (mg)	Quantity of Gelucire 50/13 (mg)	% EE [Y1]	Particle size (nm) [Y2]
NS1	-1,-1	500	200	67.79	216.25
NS2	-1,0	500	250	58.97	203.81
NS3	-1,+1	500	300	54.34	200.43
NS4	0,-1	600	200	79.63	273.88
NS5	0,0	600	250	74.30	241.62
NS6	0,+1	600	300	69.59	234.43
NS7	+1,-1	700	200	84.27	302.09
NS8	+1,0	700	250	80.53	278.71
NS9	+1,+1	700	300	78.22	249.26

Statistical software, Stat-ease Design-Expert 9.0.4 was used to evaluate the responses i.e % EE and particle size as shown in table 23.

% Entrapment efficiency [Y1]

The first step towards an optimal statistical analysis was to select the model that best describes and fits the data. Results were analyzed by the sequential model comparison. Results of the sequential model comparison, which indicate whether a model could describe a response, are given in table 8.

Table 8: Sequential model comparison for %EE.

Source	Sequential p-value	Adjusted R-Squared	Predicted R-Squared	
Linear	0.0002	0.9258	0.8713	
2FI	0.2067	0.9373	0.8994	
Quadratic	0.0070	0.9962	0.9855	Suggested
Cubic	0.6676	0.9949	0.8831	Aliased

From the model comparison data, cubic model was shown to be aliased. For this response Quadratic model was found to be statistically significant with a p-value 0.0070.

Table 9: Model summary statistics for Y1.

Source	Std Dev	R-Squared	Adjusted R-Squared	Predicted R-Squared	PRESS	
Linear	2.78	0.9443	0.9258	0.8713	106.90	
2FI	2.55	0.9608	0.9373	0.8994	83.56	
Quadratic	0.63	0.9986	0.9962	0.9855	12.04	Suggested
Cubic	0.73	0.9994	0.9949	0.8831	97.12	Aliased

After comparing the different models for parameters like standard deviation (SD), R^2 , adjusted R^2 , predicted R^2 and predicted residual error sum of squares (PRESS) from table 9, the best fit model suggested by software was Quadratic model with lowest PRESS value of 12.04.

The Model F-value of 416.22 implies the model is significant. There is only a 0.02% chance that an F-value this large could occur due to noise. Values of "Prob > F" less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant. In this case A, B, AB, A^2 are significant model terms (Table 10).

Table 10: ANOVA for Response surface quadratic model.

Source	Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom (df)	Mean Square	F Value	p-value Prob > F	
Model	829.49	5	165.90	41.22	0.0002	Significant
<i>A-lipid</i>	639.01	1	639.01	1603.24	<0.0001	
<i>B-Gelucire</i>	145.44	1	145.44	34.89	0.0003	
<i>AB</i>	13.69	1	13.69	34.35	0.0099	
A^2	29.18	1	29.18	73.22	0.0034	
B^2	2.16	1	2.16	5.43	0.1022	
Residual	1.20	3	0.40			
Cor Total	830.68	8				

Table 11: Model summary statistics for response Y1.

Std. Dev.	0.63	R-Squared	0.9986
Mean	71.96	Adj R-Squared	0.9962
C.V. %	0.88	Pred R-Squared	0.9855
PRESS	12.04	Adeq Precision	59.142

The "Pred R-Squared" of 0.9855 is in reasonable agreement with the "Adj R-Squared" of 0.9962; i.e. the difference is less than 0.2. "Adeq Precision" measures the signal to noise ratio. A ratio greater than 4 is desirable. Your ratio of 59.142 indicates an adequate signal. This model can be used to navigate the design space (Table 11).

Contour and Response Surface Plots

Contour plots and Response surface plots were useful in the study of the effect of two factors on a response at a time.

The Contour plot (Figure 5) and Response surface plot (Figure 6) shows that as the concentration of lipid increases, the % EE increases and as the concentration of surfactant increases, the % EE decreases. This may be due to as the concentration of lipid increases, it entraps more amount of drug in lipid, hence less quantity of drug remains free in dispersion which in turn increases % EE while as the concentration of surfactant increases, some part of the drug may get partitioned in the surfactant solution and hence, % EE decreases.

Figure 5: Contour plots showing the effect of concentration of lipid and surfactant on %EE.

Figure 6: Response surface plots showing the effect of concentration of lipid and surfactant on %EE.

Particle size [Y2]

From the model comparison data, cubic model was shown to be aliased. For this response 2FI model was found to be statistically significant with a p-value 0.0528 (Table 12).

Table 12: Sequential model comparison for particle size.

Source	Sequential p-value	Adjusted R-Squared	Predicted R-Squared	
Linear	0.0002	0.9176	0.8316	
2FI	0.0528	0.9565	0.9181	Suggested
Quadratic	0.1928	0.9758	0.9191	
Cubic	0.8303	0.9500	-0.1393	Aliased

Table 13: Model summary statistics for Y2.

Source	Std. Dev.	R-Squared	Adjusted R-Squared	Predicted Squared	R- PRESS	
Linear	10.09	0.9382	0.9176	0.8316	1663.76	
2FI	7.33	0.9728	0.9565	0.9181	808.90	Suggested
Quadratic	5.46	0.9909	0.9758	0.9191	798.67	
Cubic	7.86	0.9937	0.9500	-0.1393	11254.56	Aliased

After comparing the different models for parameters like standard deviation (SD), R^2 , adjusted R^2 , predicted R^2 and predicted residual error sum of squares (PRESS) from table 29, the best fit model suggested by software was 2FI model with lowest PRESS value of 808.90. The Model F-value of 59.67 implies the model is significant. There is only a 0.02% chance that an F-value this large could occur due to noise. Values of "Prob > F" less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant. In this case A, B is significant model terms (Table 14).

Table 14: ANOVA for Response surface 2FI Model.

Source	Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom (df)	Mean Square	F Value	p-value Prob > F	
Model	9609.97	3	3203.32	59.67	0.0002	Significant
A-lipid	7319.93	1	7319.93	136.36	<0.0001	
B-Gelucire	1947.60	1	1947.60	3.28	0.0018	
AB	342.44	1	342.44	6.38	0.0528	
Residual	268.41	5	53.68			
Cor Total	9878.38	8				

Table 15: Model summary statistics for response Y2.

Std. Dev.	7.33	R-Squared	0.9728
Mean	244.50	Adj R-Squared	0.9565
C.V. %	3.00	Pred R-Squared	0.9181
PRESS	808.90	Adeq Precision	21.679

The "Pred R-Squared" of 0.9181 is in reasonable agreement with the "Adj R-Squared" of 0.9565; i.e. the difference is less than 0.2. "Adeq Precision" measures the signal to noise ratio. A ratio greater than 4 is desirable. Your ratio of 21.679 indicates an adequate signal. This model can be used to navigate the design space (Table 15).

Contour and Response Surface Plots

Contour plots and Response surface plots were useful in the study of the effect of two factors on a response at a time.

Figure 7: Contour plots showing the effect of concentration of lipid and surfactant on Particle Size.

Figure 8: Response surface plots showing the effect of concentration of lipid and surfactant on Particle size.

The Contour plot (Figure 7) and Response surface plot (Figure 8) shows that as the concentration of lipid increases, particle size increases since at high lipid concentration, there is a tendency of lipid to coalesce. As the concentration of surfactant increases, the particle size decreases which may be due to the surfactant-induced reduction in surface tension between aqueous phase and lipid phase, thus preventing particle aggregation.

The Stat-Ease Design Expert 9.0.4 Software showed that the formulation containing Lmix (656 mg) and total surfactant concentration (200 mg) was optimum as shown in table 16 and was subjected to further dosage form development.

Table 16: Optimized formula of NLCs dispersion.

Ingredients	Quantity
Ziprasidone Hydrochloride Monohydrate	40 mg
Preciro ATO 5	459.20 mg
Labrafi M1944	196.80 mg
Geucire 50/13	200 mg
Distilled Water	q.s to 10 ml

Overlay plot:

An overlay plot was obtained using Design-Expert 9.0.4 software, to determine quantity of both the independent variables i.e. amount of Lmix and total surfactant concentration to obtain dispersions having % EE in range of 54-84% and particle size in range of 200-302 nm. Figure 9 shows the overlay plot of dependent variables i.e. the % EE (Y1) and particle size (Y2) at different values of independent variables i.e. amount of Lmix (X1) and concentration of total surfactant (X2).

From the above plot, it can be concluded that optimum level of total Lmix and surfactant concentration favors the desired % EE and particle size of formulation.

Figure 9: Overlay Plot.

Evaluation and characterization of NLCs dispersion

a) % Entrapment efficiency (% EE):

The independent parameters such as lipid concentration and surfactant concentration affect the dependent variables such as % EE. The % EE for various factor level combinations was found in the range of 54.34% to 84.27%. The % EE increased when the concentration of total lipid was increased from 3 to 7% due to the increase in solubility of ZHM in Precirol ATO 5 and Labrafil M1944. The % EE of ZHM significantly decreased on increasing the concentration of total stabilizer from 200 to 300 mg. The EE of optimized formulation predicted was 82% but it was found to be 83.33%.

b) Particle size:

Particle size distribution is one of the most important characteristics for the evaluation of the stability of colloidal systems. The predicted particle size of optimized formulation was 283.94 nm but in actual it was found to be 266.15 nm. The Poly Dispersity Index (PDI) gives information about the homogeneity of particle size distribution in the system. A small value of PDI is indication of narrow size distribution in the system whereas large value indicates wide size distribution in the system. The PDI of optimized NLCs batch was found to be 45.79% which indicates that there is narrow particle size distribution and hence stable for longer duration of time. The distribution diagram and correlation function diagram of optimized batch of NLC is shown in figure 10 and 11 respectively.

Figure 10: Distribution diagram of optimized NLC formulation.

Figure 11: Correlation function diagram of optimized NLC formulation.

c) *In-vitro* drug release study:

There was an initial burst of drug release attributed to surface associated drug, followed by slow release as drug entrapped inside the particle diffused out in to the release medium. *In-vitro* drug release was performed for optimized NLC dispersion of ZHM as shown in figure 12. About 24 % of loaded ZHM was released from the dialysis bag within first 2 hours, followed by the release of 98.62 % within 24 hours. The occurrence of initial drug release clearly indicates the location of certain amount of ZHM onto the surface of NLCs, whereas the sustain release profile suggests the release of ZHM from the core of lipid matrix to the release medium. There is a relation between drug release and the mean particle size for NLC release study. The smaller particles have a higher surface area which gives the more initial drug release and hence prolonged sustained release. This will result in the enhancement of the absorption of the drug, which will in turn reduce the presystemic metabolism; increase the bioavailability of the drug, initiate rapid onset of action and thus will decrease the dosing frequency and dose related side effects of the drug.

Figure 12: *In-vitro* drug release profile of optimized NLC dispersion of ZHM.

Selection of cryoprotectant

For NLC dispersion, best results were obtained with 2 % of trehalose. As the concentration of trehalose was increased from 1.5 to 3 %, the appearance becomes better and particle size decreases as shown in table 33. The particle size and % EE at trehalose concentration of 2 % and 3 % were nearly same. While in case of D-mannitol and sucrose, at lower concentration the product was not properly freeze dried and was wet. At higher concentration, the product was completely dried but particle size obtained on reconstitution of freeze dried product was much more than NLC dispersion before freeze drying.

Table 17: Selection of cryoprotectant for NLC dispersion.

Batch No.	Cryoprotectant	Concentration (%)	Appearance	% EE	Particle Size (nm)	PDI
1		1	+	79.23	421.15	0.5433
2	Trehalose	1.5	++	81.11	398.46	0.4452
3		2	++	83.33	266.15	0.3216
4		1	-	--	--	--
5	D-Mannitol	1.5	-	--	--	--
6		2	+	81.70	518.38	0.6506
7		1	-	--	--	--
8	Sucrose	1.5	-	--	--	--
9		2	+	80.27	385.08	0.4579

(-) Undesirable, (+) Good, (++) Best and (--) Not acceptable/poor.

Hence, 2% of trehalose was selected as optimum concentration of cryoprotectant for freeze drying purpose. The particle size and % EE of freeze dried optimized NLC formulation were found to be 266.15 nm and 83.33 % respectively while same for NLC dispersion were 223.73 nm and 84.27 % respectively.

e) X-ray diffraction study:

Figure 13, 14, 15 and 16 shows the characteristic XRD peaks of pure ZHM, Lmix, blank and drug loaded freeze dried NLC respectively. In this study, the characteristic peaks for ZHM and Lmix were not seen in the diffraction pattern of the optimized NLC freeze dried product. From this we can conclude that ZHM was completely incorporated into NLC freeze dried powder and remains in the amorphous form.

Figure 13: X-ray diffraction pattern of pure ZHM.

Figure 14: X-ray diffraction pattern of Lmix.

Figure 15: X-ray diffraction pattern of blank freeze dried NLC.

Figure 16: X-ray diffraction pattern of drug loaded freeze dried NLC.

f) DSC study:

DSC studies were performed to investigate the physical state of the drug in the NLC, because this aspect could influence the *in-vitro* and *in vivo* release of the drug from the system. Different combinations of drug/lipid may co-exist in the lipidic carriers, such as: (i) amorphous drug either in an amorphous or a crystalline lipid and (ii) crystalline drug in either an amorphous or a crystalline lipid.

Moreover, a drug may be present either as a solid solution or solid dispersion in an amorphous or crystalline lipid. ZHM showed a sharp endothermic peak at 300.09°C corresponding to the melting as shown in preformulation. The melting peak of pure drug was totally disappeared in the thermogram of freeze dried NLC (Figure 17), evidencing the absence of crystalline drug in the NLC powder. The absence of drug melting peaks in the DSC thermogram are usually signs of dissolved, amorphous or molecularly dispersed drug within the lipid or interactions between the drug and the lipid (a plasticizing effect of the drug) or a polymorph change of the drug which can be detected as peak shifts in the DSC thermogram. Therefore, it could be concluded that ZHM in the NLCs was either in an amorphous, molecular dispersion or a solid solution state in the lipid matrix after the production as there is complete disappearance of the endothermic peak. The endothermic peak at 94.0°C indicates melting point of the Lmix in the NLC formulation. The endothermic peak at 48.90 °C indicates melting point of GrLucire50/13. The peak at 150.10°C in NLC is endothermic peak of cryoprotectant (Trehalose).

Figure 17: DSC thermogram of freeze dried NLC powder.

g) *In-vitro* drug release study:

Figure 18: Comparison of *In-vitro* drug release profile of NLC capsule and marketed conventional capsule of ZHM.

The figure 18, shows comparative release of ZHM from NLC capsule and marketed conventional capsule. The drug release from marketed conventional capsule at the end of 8hrs hrs was found to be 94.16 and from NLC capsule at the end of 24hrs was found to be 98.62 %. It was also clear that in case of NLC capsule, drug was released in linear pattern during initial stage followed by a sustained release. About 29.08 % of loaded ZHM was released from the capsule within the first 2 hrs. The occurrence of initial drug release clearly indicates the location of certain amount of ZHM onto the surface of NLCs, whereas the sustain release profile suggests the release of ZHM from the core of lipid matrix to the release medium. While in case of marketed conventional capsule, the drug was initially released in a linear pattern.

Table 18: Kinetics model fitting for NLC capsule and marketed conventional capsule.

Formulation	Models (R^2 value)				
	Zero Order	First Order	Higuchi	Korsmeyer-Peppas	Hixon-Crowell
NLC Capsule	0.9241	0.9562	0.9107	0.9810	0.9749
Zipsydon (Conventional Capsule)	0.7074	0.9889	0.9845	0.9967	0.9439

The model that best fits the release data was evaluated by regression coefficient (R^2). R^2 value was used as criteria to choose the best model to describe the drug release from the formulation.

After comparing the R^2 values of different kinetic models, the R^2 value of Korsmeyer-Peppas model was found to be closest for NLC capsule and value of first order model was found to be closest for marketed capsule (Table 18). Thus it can be concluded that drug release kinetics of the NLC capsule and marketed S.R. tablet formulations corresponds best to Korsmeyer-Peppas model and first order model of drug release respectively.

Stability studies

a) Appearance:

The appearance of the freeze dried NLC powder was good as shown in table 32 which indicated that the formulation was stable for the period of 90 days.

Table 19: Appearance of optimized formulation subjected to stability study.

Sample	Storage condition	0 day	30 days	60 days	90 Days
NLC capsule	30°C/ 65% RH	+++	+++	+++	+++
	40°C/ 75% RH	+++	+++	+++	+++

(+++)
Good.

b) *In-vitro* drug release:

Initially, the drug release from the NLC capsules at the end of 24 hours was found to be 98.62 %. The similar release profile was obtained for the NLC capsules at the end of 30, 60 and 90 days as shown in table 20 which showed that formulation was stable.

Table 20: *In-vitro* drug release of optimized formulation subjected to stability study.

Sample	Storage condition	% Cumulative drug release at 24 hours			
		0 day	30 days	60 days	90 Days
NLC capsule	30°C/ 65% RH	98.62	97.85	97.16	96.54
	40°C/ 75% RH	98.62	97.85	97.77	96.81

Figure 20: *In-vitro* drug release profile of NLC optimized formulation subjected to stability study (40°C/ 75 %RH, 2 months).**d) Particle size**

Initially, the particle size of optimized freeze dried NLC was found to be 283.02 nm. The particle size at the end of 30, 60 and 90 days was increased marginally as shown in table 21. But it was found to be within permissible limits.

Table 21: Particle size of optimized formulation subjected to stability study.

Sample	Storage condition	Particle size (nm)			
		0 day	30 days	60 days	90 Days
NLC capsule	30°C/ 65% RH	266.15	273.88	278.71	282.56
	40°C/ 75% RH	266.15	274.64	280.00	292.23

Figure 21: Distribution diagram of optimized NLC lyophilised formulation at 0 day.

CONCLUSION

Thus it was concluded that high-shear homogenization technique followed by ultrasonication method was an optimized technique for the preparation of NLC containing ziprasidone HCl monohydrate. Further future research is to be carried out such as animal studies and clinical studies

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors state no conflict of interest and have received no payment in preparation of this manuscript.

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